

Active journals indexed in Scopus that adopt the Arabic Language (Updating List September 2023)

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Abstract:

This work aims to help researchers who want to publish in Arabic Language by simplifying the search process for Active journals indexed in Scopus that adopt the Arabic Language.

We have arranged these Active journals into one brief file, and we have also added:

- Ranking journals by quartiles.
- Direct links to Home page of Journals.
- Links to the Scopus Preview.

Introduction

Many researchers face the problem of publishing in Arabic in indexed journals, which requires facilitating the process of searching for journals that adopt the Arabic Language.

Regarding list of journals Indexed in Scopus that adopt the Arabic Language (Updating List May 2023) It was previously published by (Benziane, 2023), But that work included only the list and did not include any additions, While our work more updating based on Scopus (Scopus, 2023), and includes classifying journals, providing direct links, as well as Quartile ranking journals to facilitating and simplifying the search process for Active journals indexed in Scopus that adopt the Arabic Language.

Method

We used Scopus source list (Updating List September 2023), and we searched for: Direct links to Home page of all Journals, and journals links on scopus.

Conclusion:

Through this work, we found that there are only 29 Active journals that accept publication in the Arabic language, and out of 29 journals, there are only two journals in the first quartile in the global ranking of journals, and there is only one journal concern about subject of Economics, Econometrics, and Finance.

Table 2 : Journals with: Source Title, Quartile, Direct links, and Scopus links

N	Source Title (Medline-sourced journals are indicated in Green)		Links	scimagojr.com / Scopus.com
1	Al-Jami'ah	Q1	https://aljamiyah.or.id/index.php/AJIS	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100322122&tip=sid&clean=0
2	Arab Journal of Forensic Sciences and Forensic Medicine	Q4	https://journals.nauss.edu.sa/index.php/AJFSFM/index	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21101052922&tip=sid&clean=0
3	Arab Journal of Plant Protection	Q4	https://arabjournalpp.org/	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100819201&tip=sid&clean=0
4	Baghdad Science Journal	Q3	https://bsj.uobaghdad.edu.iq/index.php/BSJ	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100840337&tip=sid&clean=0
5	Brill Studies in Middle Eastern Literatures	Q2	https://brill.com/display/serial/BSME?language=en	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100455924&tip=sid&clean=0
6	Dirasat: Human and Social Sciences	Q3	https://dsr.ju.edu.iq/djournals/index.php/Hum	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=5600153254&tip=sid&clean=0
7	Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal	Q3	https://www2.cloud.editorialmanager.com/emh/j/default2.aspx https://www.emro.who.int/emh-journal/eastern-mediterranean-health-journal/about-the-journal.html	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=20214&tip=sid&clean=0
8	Global Journal Al-Thaqafah	Q3	http://www.gjat.my/	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100324067&tip=sid&clean=0
9	Handbook of Oriental Studies. Section 1, The Near and Middle East	Q3	https://brill.com/display/serial/HO1?language=en	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100426624&tip=sid&clean=0
10	Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Sciences	Q2	https://jcoagri.uobaghdad.edu.iq/index.php/intro	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100809798&tip=sid&clean=0
11	Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Sciences	Q2	https://www.vetmedmosul.com/	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=19500157815&tip=sid&clean=0
12	Iraqi National Journal of Earth Science		https://earth.mosuljournals.com/	https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21101141752?fbclid=IwAR0n4EpTz7oPqgJ_T5ZDNhNjOPHvBRbDkAq17AJaXFXkV-WL5FsEENB-0
13	Islam Tetkikleri Dergisi	Q2	https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/iuislamtd	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21101101951&tip=sid&clean=0
14	Islamic History and Civilization	Q2	https://brill.com/display/serial/IHC?language=en	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100407919&tip=sid&clean=0
15	Jordan Journal for History and Archaeology	Q3	https://journals.ju.edu.iq/jiha	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21101042995&tip=sid&clean=0
16	Journal of Islamic Manuscripts	Q2	https://brill.com/view/journals/jim/jim-overview.xml	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100403909&tip=sid&clean=0
17	Journal of King Abdulaziz University, Islamic Economics	Q4	https://journals.kau.edu.sa/index.php/JKAUIE	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=19700174646&tip=sid&clean=0
18	Journal of Qur'anic Studies	Q2	https://www.eupublishing.com/loi/JQS	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100211116&tip=sid&clean=0
19	Jurnal Ilmiah Islam Futura		https://jurnal-ar-raniry.ac.id/index.php/islamfutura	https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21101107566
20	Kufa Journal for Agricultural Sciences		https://journal.uokufa.edu.iq/index.php/kjas	https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21101132408
21	Mnemosyne, Supplements	Q2	https://brill.com/view/serial/MNS	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100407217&tip=sid&clean=0
22	Parole de l'Orient	Q4	https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21100253111	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100253111&tip=sid&clean=0
23	Philosophia Antiqua	Q2	https://brill.com/display/serial/PHA	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100407421&tip=sid&clean=0
24	Scientific Journal of King Faisal University	Q4	http://mportal.kfu.edu.sa/en/departments/sjournal/pages/desc.aspx	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=19700187504&tip=sid&clean=0
25	Studia Islamika	Q1	https://journal.uinjkt.ac.id/index.php/studia-islamika	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100407605&tip=sid&clean=0
26	Studies in the History and Society of the Maghrib		https://brill.com/display/serial/SHSM	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100406932&tip=sid&clean=0
27	Texts and Studies on the Qur'an		https://brill.com/display/serial/TSQ	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100406946&tip=sid&clean=0
28	Tikrit Journal of Engineering Sciences	Q3	https://tj-es.com/	https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21101118628
29	Ulumuna (Indonesian Journal of Islam and Muslim Societies)		https://ulumuna.or.id/index.php/ujis	https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21101121509

Source: Author

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